

SEMANTIC AND CONCEPTUAL FIELD OF SOMATIC PHRASEOLOGISMS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. This article provides a comparative analysis of the semantic and conceptual features of somatic phraseological units in English and Karakalpak languages. Somatic phraseological units are stable language expressions containing the names of human body parts, reflecting the worldview, cultural values, and cognitive models of the people. The article examines the main semantic fields such as “head/bas,” “eye/kóz,” “hand/qol,” and “heart/júrek,” highlighting similarities and differences in meaning and stylistic use across the two languages. Additionally, the cultural foundations and significance of certain idioms in translation are discussed. The findings contribute to translation studies, linguoculturology, and cognitive linguistics, providing a valuable theoretical basis for further research.

Key words. Somatic phraseological units, semantic field, conceptual field, comparative analysis, English language, Karakalpak language, translation, cognitive model, linguoculturology.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va qoraqalpoq tillaridagi somatik frazeologik birliklarning semantik va konseptual xususiyatlari qiyosiy tahlil qilingan. Somatik frazeologizmlar inson tana a'zolari nomlarini o'z ichiga olgan, xalqning dunyoqarashi, madaniy qadriyatlari va kognitiv modellarini aks ettiruvchi barqaror til iboralaridir. Maqolada "head/bas," "eye/kóz," "hand/qol," "heart/júrek" kabi asosiy semantik maydonlar o'rganilib, ikki tildagi ma'no va uslubiy qo'llanilishdagi o'xshashlik va farqlar yoritilgan. Bundan tashqari, ayrim iboralarning madaniy asoslari va tarjimadagi ahamiyati haqida so'z yuritiladi. Natijalar tarjimashunoslik, lingvomadaniyatshunoslik va kognitiv tilshunoslikka hissa qo'shib, keyingi tadqiqotlar uchun qimmatli nazariy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Somatik frazeologizmlar, semantik maydon, konseptual maydon, qiyosiy tahlil, ingliz tili, qoraqalpoq tili, tarjima, kognitiv model, lingvokulturologiya.

The language of every nation is a reflection of its national worldview, historical development, and cultural values. The phraseological composition of the language clearly reflects this worldview, the thoughts and way of life of the people. Phraseologies, as stable units of language, reflect the lifestyle, psychology, and historical experience of a nation [6:92].

Somatic phraseologies are phraseological units containing the names of parts of the human body, which are an important source for studying the cognitive models and conceptual field of the population. A comparative analysis of the semantic and conceptual features of somatic phraseological units in English and Karakalpak languages is of great importance not only linguistically, but also culturally [2:39].

Somatic phraseologisms are fixed units involving lexemes related to human body parts, such as "head/bas," "hand/qol," "eye/kóz," "heart/júrek," and "tongue/til." They are often formed on the basis of metaphor and metonymy and express the thoughts, emotional states, mental activity, or manner of action of the people [1:47].

As researchers (A.V. Kunin, Sh. Balli, O. Esperson) have noted, somatic units occupy a special place in phraseological systems because the human body is a universal concept of thoughts and feelings [3:108].

Somatic phraseological units are divided into the following types:

1. to indicate emotional state:

to lose one's head - hawlıgıw, ózin joǵaltıw.

júregi lúpildep ketiw - qattı tolqınlanıw.

2. to indicate mental activity:

to keep something in mind - este saqlaw, bası isleydi - aqıllı, oylay alatuǵın

3. to represent a physical state and action:

hand in hand - birlikte, (qoldı qolǵa berip - together)

qolı jetpeydi - imkanı joq, isley almaw

In English and Karakalpak, somatic phraseological units encompass various semantic fields. A semantic field is a network of words that share a common semantic property or refer to a specific area of experience. The words in a semantic field are related conceptually, but each has its own specific meaning. The most active semantic fields are concepts like head/bas, eye/koz, hand/qol, and heart/jurek [4:225].

1. Head (Bas)

to have a good head on one's shoulders - aqıllı bolıw.

bası isleydi - oylaydı, aqılı bar

to lose one's head - bası aynalıw, ózin joǵaltıw, albırawshılıq.

2. Eye (Koz).

in the public eye - jámiyet itibarında bolıw

kóz aldınan ketpew - yadtan shıqpaw.

to keep an eye on – qadaǵalaw, kóz salıw

3. Hand (Qol)

to give a hand — járdem beriw

qolı jetpeydi — imkanı joq

to be in good hands — isenimli qolda bolıw, jaqsı qolda bolıw

4. Heart (Jurek)

to learn by heart — yadlap alıw, yadlaw

júregi awırıw — qayǵı-hásiret shegiw

to have a big heart — sahiy, mehriyban, júregi keń adam.

As can be seen from these examples, in both languages, individual qualities, emotional states, and social relationships are expressed through body parts.

Somatic phraseology expresses the worldview and cultural heritage of the people. For example, "head" is considered a center of thought and control in English culture, while in the Karakalpak language; "bas" is associated with a person's inner state and intellect. "Heart/bas" is perceived as a center of feeling in both languages. This is a universal concept and occupies a central place in many phraseological units. Cultural differences are evident in some idioms. For example, "to have green fingers" (ósimlik ósiriwge uqıplı bolıw) does not have a direct equivalent in the Karakalpak language and should be given through descriptive translation.

In conclusion in both languages, somatic phraseological units are important linguistic units expressing the cognitive model and national mentality of the population. Although they share many common concepts, some cultural differences are reflected in the semantic and stylistic aspects of phraseology.

Comparative analysis can lead to important scientific results in the fields of translation, linguoculturology, and cognitive linguistics. Studying the semantic and conceptual fields of somatic phraseologies allows for a deeper understanding of their place in the worldview of the people and their significance in translation [5:84].

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